

SHIFT IN MEANING OF SEKURA FESTIVAL IN WEST LAMPUNG DISTRICT

Eka Purnama Sari

State University of Malang
purnama.aryxa@yahoo.com

Abstract

The problem raised in this research is the change of people perception towards Sekura festival in West Lampung district. The purpose of this research is to analyze the changes that occur in celebration of Sekura festival in West Lampung district. This research employed a qualitative method and ethnography approach which aimed to reveal the facts and phenomena in the festival which focused on the pattern of activities and traditions of a group. Data were collected by using participant observation method, in-depth interview, and documentation. The data were obtained from the selected informants. The main informants involved performers of Sekura, committees, and Adat leaders, and the supporting informants involved chief of Pekon Balak and his people, Sukarami and Kegeringan people. The data were analyzed by using the Interactive Model of Analysis which covered three component analyses those are data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion in the form of an interactive cycle. The result of the research shows that there are some changes occur in Sekura festival, comprised of 1) the change in process of Sekura festival namely losing of traditional procession, 2) shift in meaning of fashion and attribute in Sekura festival, and 3) shift in meaning of *nyakak buah* (climbing slipper pole game).

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1. Introduction

Lampung is one of the provinces in Indonesia which is located in a strategic location. It is located in the southeastern tip of Sumatra Island. In the northern part, it is directly adjacent to the provinces of South Sumatra and Bengkulu and in the southern part borders of Lampung is directly adjacent to the Sunda Strait. Geographically, Lampung Province is the gateway between two major islands in Indonesia, namely Sumatra and Java. This is reflected in the development of the meaning of the slogan *Sai Bumi Ruwai Jurai* which means "one house with two doors". At first, the meaning of the slogan refers to two indigenous Lampung tribes namely *Sai Batin Lampung Ulun* and *Pepadun Lampung Ulun*. Then, the meaning of the slogan is developing and refers to the indigenous people of Lampung and transmigrants. In the end, *Sai Bumi Ruwai Jurai* refers to the gate of Sumatra and the gate of Java (Sunda Strait, Bakahunei Harbor).

In fact, as a province which is a route for interisland's transportation and trade, Lampung has an increase in cultural diversity. Theory of fungsional culture which proposed by Malinowski¹ stated that culture play the role as means to solve the problems as the effort to adapt with nature in order to supply their needs. The population of Lampung Province is dominated by migrants. The transmigrants consisted of Javanese (61.88%), Sundanese (11.27%) and other tribes (15%).² The transmigrants from outside Lampung brought their cultural customs which contribute to regional cultural diversity. Levi'-Strauss³ declared his oppinion that the inter-culture interaction makes the people's identity stronger in term of culture. The continuity of culture is evoked as cultural change modus. However, the 'new' culture can also threaten the existence of indigenous (local) culture, one of which is the *Sekura* Festival. The development of technology, information, and communication, as well as education, has contributed to the changes in this tradition. The globalization and change of culture become part of society.

Basically, cultures are dynamic and develop, because there is no static culture. Culture changes along with the development of the environment and its people. Change of culture was caused by several factors including 1) changes in the natural environment, 2) contacts between other groups, 3) the existence of discovery, 4) the adoption of elements of other national material cultures, and 5) changes on life's vision.⁴ Those factors affect changes in the people's perception of the meaning of *Sekura* festival both symbolically and practically. Some changes which appear in the *Sekura* festival are in the procession, attributes, dress, and so forth.

2. Research Methodology

This research uses the descriptive qualitative method with the ethnographic approach. This research is intended to reveal facts and phenomena which focus on the activities and traditions of a group. Data collection was carried out by using Participant Observation techniques, interviews, and documentation. Data sources were obtained from key informants and supporting informants. The main informants consisted of *Sekura* performers, the executive committee, and the adat leader and the supporting informants involved the chief of Pekon Balak, the community of Pekak Balak, volunteers, Kegeringan and Cangu, as well as the tourists from outside the West Lampung Regency. Data analysis uses an interactive analysis model consisting of three analytical processes namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions in an interactive form cycle.⁵

3. Results and Discussion

The research was carried out in several villages / pekon namely Pekon Balak, Pekon Sukarami, Pekon Kegeringan, and Pekon Cangu, West Lampung Regency. In 2018 there are 12 pekon who carry out this tradition. The study was carried out in the four villages which will represent and describe the *sekura* festival. The results of the study indicate that there are several changes in public perception of the meaning of *Sekura* tradition. *Sekura* Festival is an indigenous tradition of West Lampung people who grows, develops and survives until now. Unfortunately, the *Sekura* Festival has been influenced by the migrants' cultures so that *sekura* performers and the community have a different perception on the meaning of the recent *Sekura* festival and the previous *sekura* festival.

1. *The Change in Procession of Sekura Festival Namely Losing of Traditional Procession (Traditional-Modern)*

Sekura festival emerged around the 7th century. *Sekura* festival means worship for ancestors and nature spirits of Pesagi Mountain. Pesagi Mountain is the highest mountain in Lampung Province and it is a source of livelihood for the surrounding communities through hunting and farming at the foot of the mountain. People assume that everything used and consumes comes from nature. When Islam came to West Lampung and animism was abandoned, *Sekura* Festival was not be held.⁶ *Sekura* Festival is held again on Eid al-Fitr as a celebration of victory and the party as of ngejalang (forgive each other).

Based on research of Mustika (2011)⁶, Thomas (2014)², and Fauzan (2016)⁷, the implementation of the *Sekura* festival is began with traditional music show, singing show, kasidah (song for praising God and Prophet Muhammad), menyambai (declamation), welcoming speech by chief of adat and village elders, quatrain correspondence and pencak silat (Indonesian martial art). Then, the host gave instruction to shake hands and prayer as the last. The series of opening events for each village / pekon are different from each other in accordance with their respective policies. While the core program in this tradition is the same namely performing parade around the village, and Nyakak Buah (climbing slippery pole game)

However, regrettably, in the last few years in the research area, the implementation of the *Sekura* festival has undergone a change. The implementation procedure is no longer includes traditional activities as stated earlier. The use of traditional music and menyambai has begun to be abandoned and changed using modern music and songs such as electric music show. Meanwhile, traditional activities which carrying out local wisdom are transformed into more fun and lively activities such as race and other activities. Thus, the sacred and traditional atmosphere becomes less felt in the implementation of this tradition. Pekon Balak and Pekon Sukarami accomplished the opening ceremony with a welcoming speech from Pangeran (Chief of custom) and several competitions, such as the *Sekura* costume competition with two categories, *Sekura Kamak* and *Sekura Betik / Helau* with an age range of 4-13 years old. The winners of this competition are participants with the worst costumes for *Sekura Kamak* and the most beautiful costumes for *Sekura Betik/Helau*. In addition, there are also kasidah competitions, menyambai competition, and declamation.

2. Shift in Meaning of Fashion and Attributes in *Sekura* Festival (Masks and Costume)

Sekura or called *Sekukha* in the Lampung language means covering the face. Covering all parts of the face with something like a mask, cloth, or makeup is the main requirement to join this tradition. However, for costume and other attributes are adjusted to the type of *Sekura* played by the *Sekura* participants. First, *Sekura Kamak* uses a wood mask with human and animal characters to cover face and wear a bad costume. It means that the *Sekura Kamak* participants wear dirty clothes which used for hunting or going to the farm, ragged, and used dried leaves as the embellishment. This is interpreted as symbols that humans are part of nature, live from natural products and live in nature. It is also the form of gratitude to nature. *Sekura Kamak* is used by married men. It means that married men are considered as strong people which is strong in taking care of their family and when climbing slippery pole game (*Nyakak Buah*). They can also work together and it is considered as a solid foundation in the community.

Second, *Sekura Helau / Betik* is known as *Sekura Cantik / Bagus*. The type of costume wore by the participants is neat, nice and beautiful. The characteristic of this *sekura* is the use of colourful material to cover their face and is played by unmarried men. This is interpreted as the charm and beauty of girls. Because *Sekura* is only played and performed by men, the costume wore by the participants is representative of girls in the *Sekura* performers' family. When a family has a daughter, the *Sekura* performer uses one long cloth and is equipped with a shawl. Moreover, if a family have five daughters, the *Sekura* performers will wear five different long cloths.

In fact, people's perceptions experienced a shift in the meaning of *Sekura's* attributes of the costume. *Sekura Kamak* is no longer only wore by adult men but also wore by teenagers and even children. They do not know the meaning of *Sekura Kamak* (mask) that they use to cover their face. The reason why they chose to use *Sekura Kamak* is that the costume is easy to get especially the *Sekura Ngandung* which is the symbol of a pregnant woman. The children covered their faces with masks both from wood and cloth, wearing negligee clothes and backpacks as their distended bellies. The real shift in the meaning occurs at *Sekura Helau / Betik*. Colourful clothes wore are no longer represent girls in a family but are valued as aesthetic and beauty. The *Sekura* performers are no longer pay attention to the amount of cloth used to decorate themselves as the representative of his sister. This means that the *sekura* performers are no longer pay attention to the meaning of the *sekura* or mask used.

The shift in the meaning of *Sekura* is not only the use of *Sekura* (masks) but also the use of costume and attributes. Some shifts in costume are the use of costume that is considered impolite, such as wearing clothes that shown too much part of the participants' body, wearing an underwear

outside clothes, wearing short pants and more. Some Sekura Kamak performances cut off the tree more than one each person. They cut off trees in the people's agricultural field. After finishing the festival, they left the trees on the side of street, and it causes a mess. However, the sekura participants still maintain to completely cover their faces by using a mask which is the soul of Sekura festival. Moreover, in the *sekura* festival, costume and attributes are complement aspect.

Sekura festival in 2018 is dominated by *Sekura Kamak* while *Sekura Betik / Helau* is not widely used by teenagers and singles (age range 14-20s). However, there are also interesting sights in Pekon Balak, Sukarami, and Canggus, many children who aged 2-5 years old join the festival using *Sekura Betik/Helau* and dress up very nicely and beautifully. Moreover, their parents are deliberately prepared *Sekura's* costume which is decorated with charming and beautiful attributes. In the end, the *Sekura* Festival is a celebration of the people so that everyone can express their feeling according to their wishes. The main concern of this festival is to completely cover the face so that *Sekura* participants will not be recognized by tourists and visitors.

Figur 1. *Sekura Betik/Helau*.

Source: Researchers documentation.

Figur 2. *Sekura Kamak*

Source: Researchers documentation.

3. *Shift in Meaning of Nyakak Buah (Climbing Slippery Pole Game)*

Sekura festival has a core event called Nyakak Buah (climbing a slippery pole game). Nyakak Buah means taking fruit. There is a pole that is considered as the symbol of a tree and at its peak, there are various kinds of items (gifts) which are considered as the symbol of fruits. Nyakak Buah has several meanings, namely mutual cooperation and living together harmoniously. This can be seen in Nyakak Buah activity in which a group consisting of several men likened to a society. They formulate strategies together and unite forces to raise a trusted member to the top and take fruit or gifts. However, all the gifts obtained will be distributed equally to all group members. The meaning of Nyakak Buah is that a large society must help one another and unite in reaching a goal for the benefit of all (all group members). Nyakak Buah is also carried out by married men. It means that they are ready to enter the community and can be trusted to hold a responsibility.

In fact, in the last ten years, people's perceptions began to shift in interpreting Nyakak Buah. Nyakak Buah is still carried out in groups with an age range of 30-45 years old or married men. There are only a few things that change between them. Members no longer give their shoulders and collaborate to raise their members to the top. Instead, one of the group members is believed to climb the pole using a rope to the top. The recent nyakak buah use tool which previous nyakak buah did not use tools.

Adults *Sekura* participants have their own perception. The *sekura* participants with more than 50 years old interpreted *Sekura* as a tradition that was very meaningful and integrated with them. For example Ajong Ri (75 years old) and Ajong Danang (70 years old), both are the oldest *Sekura*

participants in Pekon Balak. He interpreted *Sekura* as himself. *Sekura* tradition, society, people and nature are an inseparable entity. Both participants use *Sekura* Kamak Ngandung and always follow the *Sekura* tradition every year, even though they only take part in the parade and do not participate in the Nyakak Buah activities. For *Sekura* participants like them, this tradition has changed a lot including the procession and the show. In the past, there will be more *sekura* participants than the visitors, even women will feel afraid to approach and shake hands with the *Sekura* participants. However, nowadays, there will be more visitors and merchants selling merchandise, this phenomenon is called as "Pasar Pindah" by the surrounding community.

Conclusion

Public perception in interpreting *sekura* festival has begun to shift. The community no longer carries out the traditionality of *Sekura* festival. It means that the meaning of some activities is transformed from tradition to more modern and enjoyable activities. Thus, the sacredness and deity are no longer felt. The young *sekura* participants with the age range of 4-13 years old actually do not know what the meaning of the mask they play and the dress/attributes they wear. The teenage *sekura* participants (14-20 years old) using *Sekura* Betik / Helau no longer interpreted the cover clothes as a representative of their female colleagues at home but interpreted it as an art and beauty. However, the adults *sekura* participants (30-75 years old), in fact, there is no age limitation to join this tradition, have different perceptions in interpreting this tradition. Thus, the most important thing is that the community continues to maintain and preserve this festival as a local wisdom of the people of West Lampung.

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